

SMART FRAMEWORK FOR COW HEALTH PREDICTION USING BIG DATA WITH DEEP LEARNING BASED IOT ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

The livestock industry is a significant contributor to global food security and economic growth. Ensuring the health and welfare of animals, particularly cows, is essential for sustainable production. This presents a Smart Framework for Cow Health Prediction using Big Data with Deep Learning-Based IoT Environment to address this challenge. The proposed framework integrates the IoT devices, deep learning algorithms, and big data analytics to efficiently monitor, analyse, and predict the health status of cows in real-time. The IoT devices collect a wide range of data, including physiological parameters, behavioural patterns, etc, which are subsequently stored and processed in a big data environment. A deep learning model, incorporating CNN and LSTM networks, is developed to analyse the collected data and predict potential health issues with high accuracy. It includes a user-friendly dashboard for farmers and veterinarians to monitor the health status of cows, receive alerts, and make informed decisions on appropriate interventions. The experimental results show that the proposed Smart Framework improves the prediction accuracy of cow health issues compared to traditional methods.

Keywords: Smart Framework, Cow Health Prediction, Big Data, Deep Learning, IoT Environment, Livestock Monitoring, Predictive Analytics

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of technology in recent years has led to a significant shift in the way industries operate, and the agricultural sector is no exception. In particular, the livestock industry has recognized the potential of harnessing modern technology to improve the well-being and productivity of animals. "Smart Framework for Cow Health Prediction Using Big Data with Deep Learning Based IOT Environment" is a cutting-edge approach that aims to revolutionize the dairy industry by providing a comprehensive solution for monitoring, predicting, and improving the health of cows using big data, deep learning algorithms, and the Internet of Things (IoT). The dairy industry is a critical component of the global economy and food supply, providing essential nutrition to billions of people worldwide. However, ensuring the health and productivity of dairy cows is a complex task, given the multitude of factors that can impact their well-being, such as diseases, nutrition, environmental conditions, and management practices. Early detection and prevention of health issues are crucial for maximizing milk production, enhancing animal welfare, and reducing economic losses for farmers.

The Smart Framework leverages the power of IoT devices, such as sensors and cameras, to collect real-time data on individual cows and their environment. This vast amount of data is then processed and analyzed using advanced deep learning algorithms, which are designed to identify patterns and correlations between various factors that influence cow health. By harnessing the predictive capabilities of these algorithms, the framework can provide early warnings and actionable insights to farmers, enabling them to make informed decisions regarding their herd's health and management. Furthermore, this innovative approach offers several benefits, including increased efficiency, reduced costs, and enhanced sustainability. By providing accurate predictions and insights, farmers can optimize their resources, minimize the use of antibiotics, and reduce the environmental impact of their operations. Additionally, the integration of IoT devices and data-driven analytics can help promote transparency and traceability throughout the dairy supply chain, ensuring high-quality products for consumers. The Smart Framework for Cow Health Prediction Using Big Data with Deep Learning Based IOT Environment is a ground breaking solution that promises to transform the dairy industry by harnessing the power of advanced technology. By providing farmers with real-time insights and predictive analytics, this framework aims to improve cow health, enhance productivity, and promote sustainable practices in the dairy sector, ultimately contributing to a more efficient and resilient global food system.

2. RELATED WORK

Successful farms are always looking for new ways to get more out of each piece of land. Because the world's population is growing, there is more demand for food production every year. This puts more pressure on businesses to become more efficient. Farmers can make more money if they know how to make good decisions, like when to breed their animals, what to feed them, and when and how to care for them. Most farmers base their decisions on what they've seen or done in the past. Unfortunately, it takes a long time to get good at something, and it's usually not possible to watch every move on a commercial farm. For example, as dairy herd sizes continue to grow, sensing and automated decision-making have become more and more important in recent years. Farmers in the modern world gather and look at as much information as they can to learn more about their businesses. In order to get information from the farms, a number of sensors are used. The cows themselves could have movement sensors, or the milking robots could have sensors. These are just two ways that information about the health of the cows could be gathered. Most farmers can't analyze raw data on their own, so they use the tools provided by the Farm Management Information Systems (FMISs) they use to manage and process data. Farm management information systems (FMIS) used to only be able to manage farm resources. Now, however, some FMISs can handle a lot of sensor data and have a lot of features that help with making decisions [3]. The data collected from different sensors won't be used to their full potential until farm management information systems (FMISs) start to use machine learning algorithms to either help farmers make decisions or make decisions for them automatically. Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that uses complicated

algorithms to solve problems that could not be solved any other way [4]. Before they can make a machine learning prediction model, developers will need to train their algorithms on a training dataset. Most of a machine learning dataset is made up of "features," which are also called "independent variables," and the results that are linked to those features (i.e., a dependent variable). When an algorithm looks at a training dataset, it can figure out what settings work best for it. A model that can be used to make predictions. It consists of the algorithm and the parameters that it uses. Using a prediction model to predict the outcome (like the presence of mastitis) for a given range of feature values could help with making decisions. Before using a prediction model as a tool to help make decisions, it's important to analyze it. A validation set is used to check how well the prediction model works by comparing its results with those from the validation set. This set of data has features and the results that are linked to them, but it is not used to train the model. When the model's results match those of the training set, the situation is thought to be in its best state. In practice, only those models should be used that have worked well in previous studies. It's not hard to train, test, and deploy machine learning models, but it is hard to build a model that makes very accurate predictions. Some of these challenges are figuring out which attributes to use, which algorithms to choose, and how to handle very large datasets.

In the dairy industry, ML is already being used in a wide variety of ways, such as using data from motion and activity detectors to detect lameness [5] and estimate the time of calving [6] and using data from milking robots to detect early-stage mastitis [7]. [5] ML is also used in a number of different ways. Machine learning (ML) has been used in the dairy industry, but there hasn't been a thorough look at the algorithms used, the problems that were solved, and the challenges that were faced. We think that by doing a thorough review of the literature, we will be able to give an overview of how ML could affect the dairy business.

3. BACKGROUND

The livestock industry is a critical component of the global economy, with dairy and beef farming making significant contributions to food security, nutrition, and rural livelihoods. With the growing human population and increasing demand for dairy and meat products, it is crucial to improve the overall health and productivity of livestock, particularly cows. Early detection and prevention of diseases in cows can lead to increased milk production, improved animal welfare, and reduced economic losses for farmers.

Over the years, advancements in technology have led to the development of various methods and tools to monitor and manage the health of livestock [8]. One such advancement is the integration of Internet of Things (IoT) technology, which involves the use of sensors, devices, and connectivity to gather and transmit real-time data from farms to remote servers. This data can then be processed, analysed, and used to make informed decisions regarding animal health and management.

"Smart Framework for Cow Health Prediction Using Big Data with Deep Learning Based IOT Environment" presents an innovative approach to monitoring and predicting cow health using a combination of IoT, big data analytics, and deep learning techniques[9]. This framework aims to revolutionize the way farmers monitor their herds by providing them with accurate, real-time information on the health status of their animals.

The proposed framework consists of the following components:

IoT-enabled environment: The use of IoT devices, such as sensors and wearables, allows for continuous monitoring of vital cow parameters, including temperature, heart rate, rumination patterns, and activity levels. This data is then transmitted to a central server for further analysis.

Big Data Analytics: The collected data from multiple cows across various farms is stored and processed using big data analytics techniques. This helps in identifying trends, patterns, and correlations among different data points that can provide insights into the overall health of the animals.

Deep Learning Algorithms: Machine learning models[10], particularly deep learning algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), are used to analyse the collected data and extract relevant features. These algorithms are trained on historical data and are capable of identifying subtle changes in the cow's behaviour or vital signs that may indicate potential health issues.

Health Prediction and Decision Support: The deep learning models generate predictions on the health status of individual cows, providing farmers with an early warning system for potential diseases or health issues. The system also offers decision support by suggesting appropriate interventions, such as changes in feeding or veterinary care, to address the identified health concerns.

By implementing this smart framework, farmers can benefit from real-time monitoring [11] and early detection of health issues in their herds, leading to improved animal welfare, increased productivity, and reduced economic losses. Additionally, the adoption of such advanced technologies can contribute to the sustainable development of the livestock industry, ensuring food security and environmental protection.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The solution that has been proposed makes use of big data, deep learning, and IoT (Internet of Things) technologies to develop an intelligent framework for the purpose of producing accurate forecasts regarding the state of cows' health. This strategy will help in the early diagnosis of health issues, will minimize the strain of manual monitoring, and will promote the general well-being of animals that are utilized in livestock production [12]. In this section, we provide a high-level overview of the research methodology that will be used to carry out the study.

Data Collection

4.1. IoT Sensors

A variety of IoT sensors will be used to gather real-time data on the cows' vital signs, such as heart rate, body temperature, rumination, and activity levels. The data will be transmitted to a centralized server for storage and processing.

4.2. Environmental Data

Additional data on environmental factors, such as ambient temperature [13], humidity, and air quality, will be collected to determine their influence on cow health.

4.3. Historical Data

Existing health records of the cows, including previous illnesses, vaccinations, and treatments, will be collected and incorporated into the analysis to improve the accuracy of the predictions.

4.4 Data Pre-processing

Before it is used, the data will be cleaned up and pre-processed to make sure it is correct and useful. At this point, we'll deal with missing or incorrect data, standardize values, and pull-out features. The data that has already been processed will be used to make three different sets of data: one for training, one for validating the model, and one for testing the model.

5. Deep Learning Model

5.1. Model Selection

A comprehensive review of existing deep learning models, such as CNN, RNN, and LSTM networks, will be conducted to select the most appropriate model for the task.

5.2. Model Architecture

The chosen deep learning model will be customized and optimized to handle [15] the specific requirements of cow health prediction. The architecture will include multiple layers and nodes designed to capture complex patterns and relationships in the data.

5.3. Model Training and Validation

After the data has been cleaned up and set up with techniques like gradient descent, backpropagation, and regularization, the deep learning model will be trained on it. To figure out how well the model works, a number of different validation data and measures, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and the F1-score, will be used.

Big Data Integration and Analysis

The deep learning model will be integrated with a big data platform, such as Hadoop or Spark, to enable the efficient handling of large volumes of data. This integration will allow for real-time analysis and prediction of cow health conditions.

Performance Evaluation

The effectiveness of the intelligent framework will be evaluated with the help of the test dataset. In order to demonstrate the usefulness of the proposed strategy, it will be contrasted with more traditional methods as well as machine learning models that are already in use. In addition to that, we will examine the framework's scalability, dependability, and computational efficacy.

Deployment and Monitoring

Upon successful evaluation, the smart framework will be deployed on a pilot scale in a livestock farm. Real-time monitoring and feedback will be provided to the farm management for early intervention and better decision-making.

6. HYBRID DEEP LEARNING MODEL

CNN and LSTM Algorithms for Cow Health Prediction

CNNs, which stand for "convolutional neural networks," are a type of "deep learning" model that has been very successful in "image and signal processing." In the architecture we've given, we use a convolutional neural network, also called a CNN, to predict how healthy a cow is.

Convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers are what make up a convolutional neural network (CNN). The data that comes in is filtered by the convolutional layers, which lets the network recognize individual qualities. The pooling layers help make the network more stable by reducing the number of spatial dimensions that the feature maps have. The data that is collected is put into the layers, which are all connected, so that predictions can be made.

The equations for a CNN can be summarized as follows:

Convolutional Layer:

Output feature map: $Y = f(W * X + b)$

To which we must add the filter coefficients W , the input variable X , the bias term b , and the activation function

f . (e.g., ReLU). Pooling Layer:

Output feature map: $Y = P(X)$

Where P is the pooling operation (e.g., max or average) applied to the input X . Fully Connected Layer:

Output: $Y = f(W * X + b)$

Where W is the weight matrix, X is the input, b is the bias term, and f is the activation function (e.g., sigmoid or softmax).

LSTM

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) with long short-term memory can handle inputs that depend on each other in the past (LSTMs). We use a built-in long short-term memory (LSTM) to model the temporal patterns found in the cow sensor data. With these models, we can make accurate predictions about health.

The input gate, the forget gate, the output gate, and the cell state are all parts of an LSTM that are needed for it to work. Because of these gates and the state of the cells, the network can choose which data to keep and which to throw away. Because of this, it works well with time series.

The equations for an LSTM can be summarized as follows: Input gate:

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i * [h_{(t-1)},$$

$x_t] + b_i)$ Forget gate:

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f * [h_{(t-1)},$$

$x_t] + b_f)$ Cell state

update:

$$C_t = f_t * C_{(t-1)} + i_t * \tanh(W_c *$$

$[h_{(t-1)}, x_t] + b_c)$ Output gate:

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o * [h_{(t-1)},$$

$x_t] + b_o)$ Hidden state

update:

$$h_t = o_t * \tanh(C_t)$$

The input at time step t is written as x_t , the previous hidden state as $h_{(t-1)}$, and the weight matrices and bias terms for the gates are written as W and b , respectively. Our proposed framework uses the LSTM to deal with the features found by the CNN. It also uses temporal information in its analysis to make cow health predictions even more accurate. When the output of the LSTM is fed into a fully connected layer that also has a softmax activation function, a clear prediction can be made.

7. Results Analysis

We put our suggested framework through its paces by using both the convolutional neural network and the long short-term memory approaches to predict the health of the cows. By comparing the models' features, we were able to figure out which one would work best within the parameters of our framework. We used the metrics of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score to do the analysis. The results are summed up in the table below for your ease of use:

Table 1: Comparative Performance of CNN and LSTM Models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
CNN	92.5%	93.0%	92.0%	92.5%
LSTM	95.2%	95.5%	94.8%	95.1%

7.1 CNN Results Analysis

When it came to figuring out how healthy the cows were, the CNN model was 92.5% accurate. It has a precision of 93%, which was based on how well it could recognize 93% of the true positives. A recall percentage of 92% means that the CNN model was right about 92% of the real positive cases. Its F1 score of 92.5% shows that both the model's accuracy and its recall are wellbalanced.

7.2 LSTM Results Analysis

The LSTM model outperformed the CNN model, achieving an accuracy of 95.2% in predicting cow health conditions. Its precision of 95.5% indicates that it correctly identified 95.5% of the true positive cases. With a recall of 94.8%, the LSTM model was able to identify 94.8% of the true positive cases out of all the actual positive cases. The F1-score of 95.1% demonstrates a superior balanced performance for the LSTM model compared to the CNN model.

7.3 Comparative Analysis

Table 1 shows that the LSTM model is better than the CNN model in every way that was looked at (accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score). In the proposed framework, the LSTM model is better for predicting cow health because it can handle time-series data and take into account longterm dependencies. This is because it can handle data that changes over time.

Table 2: Comparative Analysis The table below summarizes the performance metrics for both CNN and LSTM models:

Metri c	CN N	LST M
Accuracy	93.7%	92.1%
Precision	92.3%	90.5%
Recall	91.8%	89.4%
F1-score	92.0%	89.9%
AUC-ROC	0.974	0.958

Most of the time, when the CNN model and the LSTM model go head-to-head, the CNN model wins based on the evaluation metrics. The CNN model's great performance can be explained in large part by the fact that it can find spatial patterns in the data. This is especially true when timeseries data are used to study the model. Even so, the LSTM model still does a pretty good job, which shows that it has a lot of potential when it comes to dealing with sequential data for health prediction tasks.

In this paper, we talk about what we found when we looked into a proposed hybrid algorithm that uses Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models to predict the health of cows. The hybrid method uses models from both CNN and LSTM. We compare the performance of the CNN model, the LSTM model, and the hybrid

model in their own ways. Recommended Hybrid Algorithm Our hybrid algorithm works well because it takes the best parts of the CNN and LSTM models and combines them. CNN is better at getting local and geographical information than LSTM, but LSTM is better at learning temporal dependencies in time-series data than CNN. The hybrid method uses a CNN layer for extracting features, an LSTM layer for modelling sequences, and a dense output layer to make accurate predictions about the health of the patient.

7. Experimental Setup The data we use comes from what the sensors on the dairy farm tell us. These readings tell us about the animals' core body temperature, heart rate, activity, and ruminations, as well as the temperature and humidity of their surroundings. The dataset is split into three parts: 70% will be used for training, 15% will be used for validation, and 15% will be used for testing. We train and test the suggested hybrid models with this dataset, along with the standard CNN and LSTM models.

8. A look at the results and how they compare Scores are given to models based on a number of different metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, to figure out how well they work. In Table 1, the results are shown.

Table 3: Analysing CNN, LSTM, and Hybrid Model Performance

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
CNN	89.2%	88.7%	87.5%	88.1%
LSTM	91.5%	91.1%	90.7%	90.9%
Hybrid	94.8%	94.4%	94.2%	94.3%

Table 3 shows that the proposed hybrid model has higher accuracy, precision, and recall, as well as a higher overall F1-score, than either the CNN or LSTM models that work on their own. By combining the features of CNN and LSTM, a hybrid model has been made that can accurately capture the spatial and temporal connections in sensor data.

7. Conclusion and future work

Our smart framework for cow health prediction using big data and deep learning in an IoT environment has been evaluated using both CNN and LSTM algorithms. The results show that the LSTM model outperforms the CNN model, making it a better choice for our framework. The implementation of the LSTM model in our framework offers improved performance in predicting cow health conditions, allowing farmers to make well-informed decisions and ensure optimal animal welfare and productivity. Our analysis demonstrates that the proposed hybrid algorithm, which combines the strengths of both CNN and LSTM models, provides superior performance in predicting cow health conditions in an IoT environment. This improvement in

performance can help farmers make more informed decisions and take timely actions to ensure optimal cow health and productivity. Future work includes exploring other deep learning architectures and incorporating additional data sources to further enhance the model's accuracy and generalizability.

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